

Derivatographic Studies of Acid Maleato Complexes of Some Divalent Metals

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Acid maleato complexes of maleic acid (Mal. H)₂ with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) of the formula [M(Mal. H)₂(H₂O)₄] [M=Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)] and [M₁(Mal. H)₂(H₂O)₂] [M₁=Cd(II)] have been studied derivatographically. A number of intermediate products were obtained which do not correspond to any simple compound but are intermediate between those of normal and acido complexes. A comparison of the different transition temperatures of the various acido complexes do not show any correlation between the thermal properties of the complex and the physical or chemical properties of metal ions.

EDGE¹ has studied the thermal decomposition of vanadyl oxyanion maleic acid complex. Mc Ginn *et al*² have also reported the thermal decomposition of normal nickel maleate [Ni(Mal)₂(H₂O)₂]. However, none have reported derivatographic studies of acid maleato complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II).

Experiment and Results

Acid maleato complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) have been prepared by our own method³. The derivatography of the system of Paulik Paulik and Erdey manufactured by M/s M.O.M.

(Hungarian Optical Works) has been employed for the

Fig. 3

Fig. 1

Fig. 4

Fig. 2

Fig. 5

present study. The instrument records the different functions (Temperature T, D.T.G., D.T.A. and T.G.A.) photographically. The instrument rules chart according to programme of time and temperature. For differential thermal analysis ignited alumina has been used as the inert material and ceramic sample holders have been used for both the test and inert substances. The material has been used loose without being packed. Thermocouple does not come in contact with material in the holders. 500 to 600 mg of finely powdered material have been employed for the test. The sample holder is kept in such a way that the tip of the thermocouple in both the holders are Pt-13 percent Rh/Pt. The height of the test material is maintained almost equal to that of inert material in the reference sample holder. About 500 to 600 mg of sample is taken in ceramic crucible and heating rate of 8°/min upto 800° is maintained in static air. Results have been presented in Table 1 and combined curves of T, D.T.G., D.T.A. and T.G.A. are presented in Figs. 1-5.

During heat treatment a volatile substance was collected over cold glass rod. It was identified to be

maleic acid by chemical analysis and m.p. determination, 131°. After heat treatment the end product in each case has been confirmed by chemical analysis and thin layer chromatography. The chemicals used were either of B.D.H. or E. Merk (A.R. Grade).

Discussion

It can be seen in general that the acid maleato complexes are completely dehydrated along with or without partial loss of ligand in first step. The composition of intermediates of first step (except Co and Zn where simply they are dehydrated) second step and third step (except Cu and Cd) do not correspond to any simple compound but are intermediate between these of normal and acido complexes. On the basis of derivatographic analysis, the acid maleato complexes may be grouped in the following two classes—

1. In this class, after dehydration and partial loss of ligand, metallic carbonate is formed which at higher temperature decomposes (a) to metallic oxide as in case of Zn-complex and (b) to free metal which

TABLE—1

	Transition	Temp. range	Curve
[Co(Mal. H) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	→ Co(Mal. H) ₂	100–170	Endothermic
Co(Mal. H) ₂	→ Co(Mal. H) _{1.70}	170–220	„
Co(Mal. H) _{1.70}	→ Co(Mal. H)	250–325	Exothermic
Co(Mal. H)	→ Co CO ₂	350–400	„
Co CO ₂	→ Co	400–560	„
Co	→ Co O	560–650	„
[Ni(Mal. H) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	→ Ni(Mal. H) _{1.85}	70–120	Endothermic
Ni(Mal. H) _{1.85}	→ Ni(Mal. H) _{1.82}	210–300	„
Ni(Mal. H) _{1.82}	→ Ni(Mal. H) _{0.80}	300–390	Exothermic
Ni(Mal. H) _{0.80}	→ NiO	390–470	„
[Cu(Mal. H) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	→ Cu(Mal. H) _{1.20}	80–190	Endothermic
Cu(Mal. H) _{1.20}	→ Cu(Mal. H) _{0.80}	190–250	„
Cu(Mal. H) _{0.80}	→ CuO	250–350	Exothermic
[Zn(Mal. H) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	→ Zn(Mal. H) ₂	75–140	Endothermic
Zn(Mal. H) ₂	→ Zn(Mal. H) _{1.13}	140–250	„
Zn(Mal. H) _{1.13}	→ Zn(Mal. H) _{0.60}	250–350	Exothermic
Zn(Mal. H) _{0.60}	→ Zn CO ₂	350–390	„
Zn CO ₂	→ Zn O	390–450	„
[Cd(Mal. H) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	→ Cd(Mal. H) _{1.44}	80–160	Endothermic
Cd(Mal. H) _{1.44}	→ Cd(Mal. H) _{0.85}	160–250	„
[Cd(Mal. H) ₂]	→ Cd O	370–410	Exothermic
CdO	→ Cd	590–700	„

is followed by oxide formation as in case of Co-complex.

2. In this class metallic carbonate is not formed as an intermediate product after dehydration and loss of ligand but decomposition of acid maleato complex leads to the formation of (a) only metallic oxide as in cases of Ni and Cu complexes and (b) metallic oxide followed by free metal as in case of Cd-complex.

A comparison of the decomposition temperatures of different acid maleato complexes do not reveal any general correlation between the thermal properties of the complexes and the physical or chemical properties of the metal ion. But the temperature at which the oxide is formed varies with the basicity of the metal $\text{Co} > \text{Ni} \sim \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Cu}$.

The deposition of maleic acid over cold glass rod is due to the thermal dissociation of the acid maleato complex to the normal complex and maleic acid

according to the reaction

and this is favoured at higher temperature. Products intermediate between normal and acido complex seems to be the incomplete thermal disproportionation. We could not conclude as to why species intermediate between acido and normal complexes are formed.

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